

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING RESEARCH METHODS IN A MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. This article focuses on the use of marketing techniques in improving marketing research. First of all, the current market situation is assessed, ie the economic situation in the market over a period of time as a result of the interaction between the factors and conditions that determine the ratio of supply and demand for products, as well as the level and price of prices.

Keywords: marketing research, conjuncture, market, Delphi method, Heuristic method, Mixed method.

Introduction. In the improvement of marketing research, attention is paid to marketing methods. First of all, the current situation in the market is evaluated - the market conjuncture, that is, the economic situation that has arisen in a certain time in the market as a result of the interaction between the factors and conditions that determine the ratio of supply and demand for products, as well as the level and movement of the prices set for them.

An important task in the study of the conjuncture is to determine the influence of certain factors on its formation and the main factors determining the conjuncture in the near future.

The following describes the state of the carpet market:

The supply and demand ratio of the product in the consumer market;

grade level;

competitive situation and barriers to market entry;

the degree of regulation of the specific market by the state;

commercial conditions of sale of services;

availability of seasonal changes in demand, etc.

It is of great interest to make a conjunctural forecast that serves as a basis for the future development of the market and the strategy and tactics of the company's activities for the production enterprise of "SAG" LLC.

In general, the current market demand in monetary terms (Q) is defined as:

$$Q = N \times G \times P,$$

Here:

N - the number of buyers of this type of goods in the market as a whole or in the market of a specific region; G - the number of purchases made by the buyer during the studied period;

P- is the average price of this commodity.

This formula is basic, but given specific types of goods, it is necessary to take into account additional factors that determine the demand for these goods. The disadvantage of these methods is that it does not take into account the competitive environment of the tourism enterprise.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Current market demand is usually determined based on the normative method. This method is used in the assessment of market potential based on the use of a number of standards and share indicators.

The disadvantage of this method is finding proportional norms and percentage indicators. Finding them will require special research. At the same time, it can be seen that the error in each multiplication goes to a new stage and the final result. To overcome this, it is possible to arrive at several estimates instead of a single estimate by using several approximations. In any case, this method should be used together with other analytical methods.

A more in-depth analysis of demand is aimed at identifying important real factors affecting the volume of sales and determining their relative impact. Factors such as prices, income levels, consumer composition, and the effect of product movement are usually analyzed frequently. When conducting such an analysis, mathematical and statistical methods are widely used.

Thus, when determining the demand, the advanced indicator method can be used. Advanced indicators are indicators or their time series that change in the direction of the studied indicator, but develop earlier than it in time. For example, the growth of indicators of the standard of living will prevail over the indicator of growth of demand.

Therefore, while studying the behavior of the indicators of the standard of living, it is possible to reach a conclusion about the approximate change of the indicator of the demand for a specific product.

Purchasing power indicators are often used to assess market potential. The purpose of this is to measure the attractiveness of the market based on the weighted average of any potential of its three main components: the number of consumer units; purchase; from the ability of consuming units; it is from the willingness to spend of consuming units.

Pre-study of conjuncture- is carried out by combining three groups of factors: objective group (population income, demographic situation, political situation, etc.); subjective (psychological characteristics, national customs, etc.); special (product range and price, attractiveness of the travel object and cheap cost, enterprise reputation, etc.).

Forecasting of the conjuncture is usually short-term, because it is possible to express the movement of the market situation only within certain limits.

When forecasting, three classes of methods are defined based on the criterion of information detail:

1. Delilographic;
2. Heuristics;
3. Mix.

Delilographic, that is, qualitative methods. These methods are based on real information about the development of the object of forecasting in the past and in the present. They are mainly used in exploratory forecasting, that is, forecasting from today to the future. Statistical methods that study the dynamic series of the forecasting object will receive special attention among the delilographic methods.

Heuristic or qualitative methods. Forecasting is based on the use of the knowledge of specialists and experts about the future development (behavior) of the object. Therefore, they are usually called expert methods. Expert methods often have jumps

corresponds to normative forecasting of processes. The most famous of them are "Attack of the mind" and "Seniktika".

The brainstorming method is based on summarizing the ideas of the participants during group discussion of the problem. On this basis, chains of thoughts appear that lead to an unexpected solution to the problem. The ideas received during the meeting are recorded and then evaluated. Brainstorming method has many implementation options.

"Senictics" is considered a intuitive and creative method of forecasting, and it is a combination of various previously incompatible elements. In this method, invited specialists from various fields of activity participate in the evaluation of experts with their own ideas created in advance. After that, separating the ideas from each other, a well-defined, popular idea is accepted.

The Delphi method is the most popular and effective in surveying experts. It has the following characteristics:

- in the first stage, each expert works separately;
- the survey of experts is carried out in several stages;
- after each passing step, the experts are introduced to other experts' estimates without knowing each other and on the basis of extensive proof of the minimum and maximum levels of the estimates.

To mixed methods mixed information bases, which include both expert method and delilographic preliminary information.

Forecasting the sales volume of a new product is a complex problem that cannot be solved by a single method. When conducting marketing research, the initial sales volume of a new product, say, within three years, is estimated. For this purpose, methods such as export methods, survey methods, and control market trading can be used.

Expert evaluations formed with marketing specialists are collected at the initial analysis stage, based on competitors' sales, potential market size, total demand, share of goods of different brands in the market, ease of access to trade relations, etc. based on data.

If the information is not sufficient, it is collected by directly asking potential customers, traders, suppliers, if possible, competitors. Market research helps to evaluate the potential sales volume of new products.

These methods are usually used together. Using the aforementioned or other approach, the marketing department must establish the future sales volume of the new product in order to launch the product.

The end of the forecasting process is the forecast, i.e. foreknowledge - verbal, mathematical, drawing or other ideas about the possible state of the travel agency itself or the tourism industry and the environment during a certain future period.

The scenario serves to fully reflect the market situation. A scenario is a description of the future. It determines the approximate development of events and the possibility of their implementation. To know the situation in advance, usually there is a certain number of possible development options, for this the forecast consists of several scenarios, it is necessary to create various freedoms for their implementation. The most reliable type of scenario is taken as the main one, and current solutions are adopted based on it.

There is a certain difference between a scenario and a forecast. A forecast is an opinion aimed at foreseeing a particular situation, based on the acceptance or elimination of its advantages or disadvantages. A scenario is a tool that determines which types of forecasts will be generated.

A firm that has information about the size of the market and trends of change will be able to assess the advantage of this or that market. If the size of the market is small, the costs of entering and operating in the market may not be covered. It should be taken into account that if the size of the market is large, it means that there is strong competition in such a market, consumers are highly grateful for the services of rivals, and the decision to choose one or another market must be taken into account with the influence of other factors.

We can divide the methods of forecasting market conditions into 4 large classes.

1. Factographic styles. This is a method of forecasting that uses real factors that have happened in the past as an informative basis. These data are quantitative and qualitative in nature. Factual methods of forecasting market conditions are divided into 3 types. The first type consists of a combination of extrapolation and interpolation methods, and the use of initial information in the construction of linear functions is characteristic for this type of model. The second type is statistical methods, which are used in the study of interactions between two or more variable predictors. The third type is based on the research of the future development of these objects according to the laws of development of similar objects.

2. Expert methods are based on the processing of opinions and opinions of experts in one or another field. The expert assessment method of forecasting includes an intuitive and an analytical method. Intuitive methods include methods based on involving experts, identifying the processes of development of the object of prediction in practice, and assessing future change through personal erudition and feeling. Analytical methods include methods based on logical analysis of the process model of the object of forecasting. Expert assessment methods, especially intuitive methods, are widely used in forecasting the market situation.

3. Method of extrapolation. Extrapolation techniques are used to predict various indicators and characteristics of the market situation. Extrapolation requires wide dissemination of laws, theories and experience of the future state of forms or processes, that is, in this case, extrapolation relies on the previous development trends of the object for which the prediction is made. One of the main models of extrapolation used in market research is the trend model. Trend models show the main directions of change in processes over time.

4. Econometric models. Econometric models are expressed by creating regression and balance equations that quantitatively describe the relationships and proportions between various indicators of the market situation, taking into account the stochastic parameters of economic processes. Econometric modeling is widely used in forecasting market conditions. They help to analyze and predict changes in production and factors affecting it, market price level, competition and factors affecting it, analysis of consumer needs, implementation of marketing activities and other processes using mathematical models.

REFERENCES

1. Golubkov E.P. Marketingovy issledovaniya: uchebnik. - M.: "Finpress", 2008. -704 p.
2. Kotler Phillip. Basic marketing. Karate course: per s English -M.: Izdatelsky dom. "Williams", 2008. -656.
3. Jalolov JJ, Fattakhov AA Business marketing. Textbook. - T.: Maliya, 2006. -355 4.Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023

4. Musaeva Sh.A. Integrated marketing communication Study guide "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand – 2022
5. MS Azimovna, RN Ulugbekovna [Development Conditions and Modern Trends of Business Tourism Worldwide](#) INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY 2 (2), 63-66
6. Kotler F. i dr. Basic marketing. - M.: LLC "ID Williams", 2013.
7. MS Azimovna [THE MAIN RESULTS OF THE LABOR PRODUCTIVITY OF THE STAFF OF THE HOTEL "BILLURI SITORA" LLC](#) Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research 11(1), 348-352
8. MS Azimovna [THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING TOOLS IN INCREASING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE ENTERPRISE](#) Science and Innovation 2 (1), 47-53
9. S Musayeva [MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 196-202
10. S Musayeva [WAYS TO IMPROVE THE POLICY OF DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN FURNITURE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 152-156
11. S Musayeva [IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES](#) Science and innovation 2 (A2), 35-40
12. MS Azimovna [Ways to Improve the Use of Marketing Information in the Assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC](#) American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343
13. MS Azimovna [Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT](#) Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 12 (3), 93-97
14. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021 <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/793>
15. Usmanov IA Musaeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. No. 2, 2021 - pp. 86-90.
16. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
17. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and installation works. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences scientific journal. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. – P. 651-658 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>
18. Usmanov IA Buriev HT A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical journal. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU-No. 4 / 2021
19. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337

20. Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna, EXAMINATION OF THE INVESTMENT PROJECT OF LEASING COMPANIES SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
21. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023